

11-16 AUGUST 2019
22nd International Conference
on Composite Materials

Study on 3D Printing and Properties of Composite Catalyst Carriers With Biomimetic Porous Structure

Cunbao Huo, Xi'an Jiaotong University, China

CONFERENCE
HOSTS:

CONFERENCE
DESTINATION
SUPPORTERS:

#ICCM22

1. Background

What is catalyst support?

Why do we use 3D printing to print the catalyst carrier?

- The demand for porous catalyst supports is increasing. The hierarchically regulated porous catalyst support has a larger specific surface area, enhances the distribution of active sites, and has excellent mass transfer between the reactants and the product.
- Conventional granular catalyst supports have poor catalytic performance. The conventional catalyst carrier and porous ceramic are complicated in manufacturing process and costly.
- 3D printing can quickly and flexibly manufacture macro-microporous structures, improve the efficiency of manufacturing catalyst carriers, enhance the catalytic performance of catalysts, and facilitate the manufacture of monolithic catalysts.

1. Background

Why do we use Powder Bed Fusion?

Turning the drawbacks into advantages, the porosity of the SLS process itself due to insufficient melting of the powder material facilitates the preparation of the porous material and the generation of through holes.

Using high-temperature sintering or melting of powder materials under laser irradiation.

2.Process for Composite Catalyst Carriers

- Fiber laser powder bed fusion 3D printer made by Xi'an Jiaotong University

Ceramic composite powder

2. Process for Composite Catalyst Carriers

- As the silica content increases, the required laser energy is reduced, the fixed preheating temperature is 55 °C, the scanning pitch is 20 μm, and the layer thickness is 150 μm:

DSC Analysis of Epoxy Resin E12

Laser power (W)	Scanning speed (mm/s)		
	1000	2000	3000
15	N	N	N
20	N	N	N
25	N	N	N
30	G	N	N

Laser power W	Scanning speed (mm/s)		
	1000	2000	3000
15	O	N	N
20	O	G	N
25	O	G	N
30	O	O	G

2.Process for Composite Catalyst Carriers

Epoxy thermogravimetric TG curve

Aluminum hydroxide thermogravimetric TG curve

- Based on the results of the above TG thermogravimetric curve, in the Beaune hot high temperature muffle furnace, the degreasing and high temperature sintering process is formulated as follows: firstly, from room temperature to 3 ° C / min to 300 ° C, then 2 ° C / min to 700 ° C. The temperature was kept at 700 ° C for 1 h, and then increased to 1200 ° C at a rate of 4 ° C / min (the other three groups of high temperature sintering temperatures were 1400 ° C, 1500 ° C, 1600 ° C) for 3 h, and cooled to room temperature with the furnace.

3.Result for Composite Catalyst Carriers

4. What to do next?

Future work:

- a. **Monolithic catalyst carrier structure design and performance simulation**
- b. **Monolithic catalyst carrier printing and catalytic performance analysis**
- c. **Preparation of high specific surface catalyst carrier**

Thanks for your attention.